

From data to impact

Insights from the Dutch Library Monitor

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Library statistics in the Netherlands go back almost to when the first public library opened in 1899 in Dordrecht. At that time mainly statistics on the number of loans and books in the collection were gathered, but this data landscape has grown considerably in the 125 years since then (Schrijen and Huwaë, 2024a). Nowadays, Dutch public libraries and policymakers have a huge volume of data on countless aspects of librarianship at their disposal, as well as various instruments for improving their services and increasing their impact by means of these data. Furthermore, the data have helped to demonstrate the importance of the library, and have contributed to the public and political reappraisal of the library that has taken place in recent years.[2]

In this paper, we discuss the central role played by the Library Monitor ('Bibliotheekmonitor') within this data landscape. After a brief sketch of the Dutch library network, we will first discuss the monitoring research conducted through this research instrument. This is first of all annual monitoring, in which we focus in particular on the so-called Data Provision regarding the Public Library Facilities System Act (hereafter: Data Provision Library Act). We then discuss continuous monitoring, which enables libraries themselves to easily visualise the output and impact of their services at no cost. In the third part of the paper, we discuss how the collected data are published and used by libraries, before concluding with a brief outlook on future developments and initiatives to increase the data maturity of the Dutch library network. We hope that the various research methods, data sources, publication formats and initiatives discussed in this paper can serve as inspiration for anyone researching

public libraries, and look forward to feedback that could help us strengthen our own research.

1. The Dutch library network

The Public Library Facilities System Act (Wsob) was introduced in 2015. It outlined the contours of the Dutch public library network, as well as everyone's roles and responsibilities within it.

In 2023, that network consisted of 133 library organisations with 1,261 library locations in the European Netherlands,[3] in addition to six library organisations with eight locations in the Caribbean part of the Kingdom of the Netherlands.[4] Under the law, these libraries perform at least five functions: making knowledge and information available, providing opportunities for development and education, promoting reading and introducing people to literature, organising meetings and debates, and introducing people to art and culture. In 2023, libraries fulfilled these functions in various ways. For example, libraries in the European Netherlands lent almost 56.8 million physical and 5.5 million digital materials to about 2.3 million youth members (69% of the population) and 1.3 million adult members (9% of the population). At the same time, the library is increasingly changing from a traditional place of lending to a broad community library at the heart of local society. This is reflected in, among other things, the record number of over 405 thousand activities organised by libraries in 2023 (KB, 2024a).

Public libraries are supported by nine provincial support institutions (POIs). Among other things, they are responsible for innovation and interlibrary loan traffic, which allows library members to request materials from other libraries' collections. They also regularly conduct research, and support libraries in working with data. Whereas the income of public libraries consists mostly of subsidies from municipalities, POIs mainly receive subsidies from the provinces.

Finally, the KB, National Library of the Netherlands plays a coordinating role in the network. It is also responsible for maintaining the

national digital library, monitoring how the network implements the law, and providing a library facility with adapted works – such as Braille books and talking books – for people with (reading) disabilities.

Cooperation in the library network was ratified in 2017 in the Library Covenant, which was also signed by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, the Dutch Association of Public Libraries, the Foundation of Cooperating Provincial Support Institutions and the umbrella organisations for municipalities and provinces. In the Library Covenant, the most recent version of which runs until the end of 2027, the various network partners agreed to commit to three societal tasks: promoting literacy and enjoyment of reading, ensuring that everyone can participate in the information society, and ensuring that everyone can continue to develop throughout their lives (Ministry of Education, Culture and Science *et al.*, 2024). An accompanying Network Agenda then worked out in practical terms how the various network partners will effect this together (VOB *et al.*, 2021).

There have been several developments in the library network in recent years. Access to libraries is becoming increasingly low-threshold: for example, an increasing number of libraries no longer require payment of fines for returning materials late, and more and more libraries offer free or reduced membership for (young) adults (Deckers, 2023; Deckers, 2025; Schrijen and Huwaë, 2024b).[5] National campaigns such as 'Discover what you can do' invest in raising awareness of the library.[6] The library also has the wind in its sails politically. A change in the law is being prepared that will oblige municipalities to provide their residents with a library that fulfils all five legal functions, and from the central government, a lot of money has recently been invested in opening or improving library locations (67 million euros), improving the (digital) public services of libraries (32 million euros) and the national programmes BookStart and the Library at School (74 million euros) (Schrijen and Huwaë, 2024c).

2. Research through the Library Monitor

Every year, much research is conducted in the Netherlands on the services, output and impact of public libraries. Much of this research is conducted through the Library Monitor. Through this online platform – facilitated by the KB in collaboration with DESAN Research Solutions – questionnaires and registration forms are used to map how libraries fulfil their social function.

This distinguishes between annual monitoring and continuous monitoring. Annual monitoring looks back at the services provided in a previous calendar year or school year. Continuous monitoring allows libraries themselves to continuously measure the output and impact of specific courses, information points and activities among participants and visitors.[7]

2.1 Annual monitoring: Data Provision Library Act

2.1.1 Themes

The aforementioned Public Library Facilities Act also plays an important role in the field of library statistics. Indeed, Section 11 of the Act stipulates that public libraries, POIs and the KB are obliged ‘for the purpose of policy development’ to provide annual data on library provision to the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. The survey used to collect these data since 2016 has come to be known as the Data Provision Library Act (‘Gegevenslevering Wsob’), and is the main source of library statistics in the Netherlands. As participation in the survey is required by law, in principle, this survey also results in data from all the public libraries and POIs.

A separate regulation with the Act specifies the themes on which data should be collected. For public libraries, that amounts to key statistics on library facilities, collection, loans, membership and visits, the fulfilment of legal functions and services, staff, and income and expenses. This can, for example, include data on the number of library members, the amount of subsidies, the number of activities organised or the

number of volunteers and staff. It always concerns data for the year preceding the year in which the survey is conducted.

In addition to key statistics, the survey can collect further information on topical issues about which there are questions in the network or at the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. For example, in the 2023 Data Provision Library Act a question was added on the extent to which libraries' subsidies were indexed for high inflation.

2.1.2 Data sources

The required data are collected from various sources. For example, Statistics Netherlands provides figures on the distance to the nearest library in each municipality, the KB's Data Warehouse provides figures and analyses on the online Library, and the Wijzer web application is a source for all data on library locations and facilities.

However, the vast majority of data comes from questionnaires completed by public libraries and POIs through the Library Monitor. These questionnaires are drawn up by the KB in consultation with the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, the trade associations of public libraries and POIs, Statistics Netherlands and experts from within the network.

In public libraries, the desired data are gathered through four thematic questionnaires. Most of the data are collected at the level of the whole organisation, but some data – such as the number of visits or housing costs – are also queried by library location. Further breakdowns are also requested for many variables. For example, we ask not only how much subsidy libraries receive or how many activities they organise, but also which subsidy streams or types of activities are involved.

While this delivers a lot of detailed data, a downside is that filling in the questionnaire can be quite a burden for libraries, especially small ones. We try to reduce that burden as much as possible. Libraries are able to access the questionnaire in preparation well before the fieldwork begins so they can start collecting the necessary data internally. They can also contact the KB with questions, and POIs offer libraries in their

province support in collecting the data. We also evaluate every stage of the survey with libraries after each edition, and make adjustments where necessary.

All data are queried as consistently as possible with previous years, although sometimes developments in the library network necessitate changes. An important trend, for example, is that more and more libraries are co-located with other organisations in combined institutions. They then share a building with several organisations (multifunctional accommodation), or are themselves part of an organisation that performs multiple functions (multifunctional organisation). This complicates the provision of data, as it is not always possible to distinguish sharply between different functions within a building or organisation. A new approach was therefore drawn up in 2023 in consultation with libraries in combined institutions. Such libraries are first asked to provide the requested data for the whole accommodation or organisation, and then to indicate as precisely as possible what part of it does not relate to the library function.

In addition to the questionnaires for public libraries, there is a separate questionnaire for provincial support institutions. Most of the questions in this are about the services and support the institution has provided to libraries in that province in the past year.

When the actual data collection starts, libraries and POIs receive an invitation e-mail with a link to the digital questionnaire in the Library Monitor. In the Library Monitor, they can also download – for reference – their answers from the previous year. Several automated checks then take place during completion that may indicate possible errors, for example when subtotals do not add up correctly to entered totals.

2.1.3 Data quality

After the data collection, a comprehensive data check and plausibility check takes place. Indeed, a mistake is easily made: if someone types in one 0 too many, it could easily mean that a library had half a million

loans, rather than 50,000. The KB and Statistics Netherlands work together on this data check. During the audit, data entered by libraries are compared (if possible) with data from previous years, with the average of libraries of similar size and with results on other questions. If a value deviates significantly from expectations, it is first considered whether this can be explained on the basis of other answers or explanations provided by the library. If not, the relevant library is asked to check the anomalous value, and share an additional explanation or correct the value in the online questionnaire.

Once all the data are collected and checked, they are given a provisional status. In the following year, libraries have one more chance to correct the data, after which the finalised data are published by the KB and Statistics Netherlands.

2.2 Annual monitoring: In-depth measurements Youth and Adults

In addition to the Data Provision Library Act, two in-depth surveys are conducted annually through the Library Monitor. These studies give more depth in how libraries fulfil their legal functions for both youth and adults and how they contribute to the societal tasks of the Library Covenant. In the questionnaires, libraries answer questions per social task about the services and activities they offer for the various target groups, how they organise this (financially and staff-wise), and what bottlenecks and successes they experience. In this regard, the survey on services for youth pays much attention to the cooperation between libraries and early childhood education and schooling. In the questionnaire about services for adults, extra attention is paid to services around basic (digital) skills, such as help with tax returns, applying for benefits and using other digital government services.

Because these questionnaires touch on many different topics, the Library Monitor allows different topics within the questionnaire to be completed by different people. This allows each library to have the questions completed by colleagues with the corresponding content expertise.

2.3 Continuous monitoring: Output

In recent years – partly due to the economic crisis and subsequent government cuts in the 2010s – it has become increasingly important for cultural organisations to be able to demonstrate their value and impact (KB, 2025a). The Library Monitor helps libraries do this by enabling them to measure the output and impact of their offerings and services themselves.

Before libraries measure impact, they record output, such as the number of people reached, the number of certificates awarded after a course or the number of visitors referred. The most comprehensive measurements are available on the so-called Digital Government Information Points (IDOs). These are points in the library where citizens can go for questions about, and help with, digital essential services, such as digital government or banking. Through the Library Monitor, libraries can record how many people visit the IDOs, what questions they come with, and how they are helped. Since the opening of the first IDO in 2019, over 273,000 queries have been registered through the IDOs. Most of these questions could be answered directly at the IDO. In addition, a visit to the IDO also regularly leads to a referral or participation in a (digital literacy) course (KB, 2025c).

2.4 Continuous monitoring: Impact

What is important, however, is not only how many people are reached by the library's services, but also what impact it has on them and society. To help libraries understand this, the KB and stakeholders (such as libraries and course providers) developed the Impact Monitor in 2019, which has now become part of the Library Monitor. This impact section within the Library Monitor consists of a collection of questionnaires that libraries can distribute (in writing or digitally) among learners or visitors after an activity, course or consultation. This examines, for example, how they experienced the activity or course, what they learnt, what skills they have now mastered, and what this means for their daily lives. This allows the library to gain insight into the impact of the service on visitors and

participants at no cost and with a standardised questionnaire, and to use these insights in the conversation with stakeholders. Moreover, the questionnaires are continuously evaluated and optimised to best suit the participants and visitors who are asked to fill them in.

The impact results of local libraries are also grouped at a national level in a dashboard. Nationally, this shows the difference the library can make for different target groups. For example, 92% of the participants of the 'Computer and Internet' courses say they are (somewhat) more confident in using the computer and the Internet after the course, and 93% of participants in courses on the Dutch language say they have (somewhat) more contact with other people after the course (KB, 2025b).

2.5 Other in-depth research

Although the focus of this paper is on the surveys conducted through the Library Monitor, many other incidental and structural surveys also result in valuable data for libraries. Linking all these research findings together provides a broader understanding of the services, output and impact of libraries.

Worth mentioning, for example, is the National Library Membership Data Collection, for which Statistics Netherlands links membership data from participating libraries to other statistical sources. This gives libraries detailed insight into the demographic of residents and households, members and non-members in their catchment area, by municipality and even by neighbourhood (KB, 2024a).

Another valuable source are the surveys initiated by the Book Trade Market Research Foundation ('Stichting Marktonderzoek Boekenvak'). This is a collaboration between the sector organisations of booksellers and publishers, the KB and reading promoters CPNB and Stichting Lezen. Four times a year, they commission surveys on reading, borrowing and buying books, among a representative panel of about 1,200 respondents. One of the surveys constitutes a regular measurement, which has been used to collect core data on reading, borrowing and buying behaviour since 2007.

The remaining three surveys are thematic surveys on topics of interest to all the partners. In recent years, for instance, studies were conducted on young people's reading preferences, parental reading training and the increase in foreign-language reading.[8]

Finally, the BiebPanel offers an example of local research: a research tool from the provincial support institution Probiblio that was developed specifically for libraries. It enables libraries to regularly conduct surveys among their (potential) target groups. The surveys cover a variety of topics, such as satisfaction, use of services, needs and expectations.

3. Use and application of data

3.1 How are the data published?

As can be seen from the above, a lot of data is collected through the Library Monitor. Partly from a legal obligation, but mainly so that libraries, policymakers and other stakeholders can use these data for policy and programme development, evaluation, optimisation and accountability. To this end, almost all collected data are made publicly and freely available, within the Library Monitor and on the public website Bnetwerk.[9] This is done in different ways so that everyone can use the data in a way that suits their own information needs and data skills.

Firstly, the most important results of the annual measurements at national level are published in online reports. In various chapters, key figures and developments are discussed, explained and visualised with interactive Microsoft Power BI graphics. When reporting the results of the Data Provision Library Act, these analyses are also complemented by articles that provide more depth and context. A key aim of these articles is to encourage an evidence-informed library practice. Regular features of this report are therefore an interview with a library on how they use the data, and a column in which a well-known person in the library world connects the data to current themes in the network.

Public libraries in the Netherlands (2023)

VISITORS AND MEMBERS

PHYSICAL COLLECTION

DIGITAL COLLECTION

ACTIVITIES

STAFF

Figure 1: Infographic showing the key national statistics of the Data Provision Library Act 2023. Libraries receive a personalised infographic in the same design, with their own data and the library's name in the title.

The results of the annual measurements are also presented in the form of infographics, which show the key statistics at a glance. Infographics are created with the data at national and provincial level, but every library and POI also receives a personalised infographic with their own organisation's data via the Library Monitor.

The results are additionally incorporated into about 50 research articles offered within Bnetwerk. Each of these articles addresses a specific topic in more detail, such as library programmes on digital literacy, the role of volunteers or diversity in the library. Regularly updated throughout the year, these articles provide up-to-date and reliable statistics, set against a broader historical and policy context. The Library Monitor surveys serve as sources for this, as well as studies from universities and other (research) partners.

The underlying data from each survey are also published, at national level, provincial level and by library organisation. For both annual and continuous monitoring, a selection of data is available in Power BI dashboards. These dashboards offer various filtering options, allowing libraries to, among other things, view their data in historical perspective or benchmark their data with similar or neighbouring libraries. Statistics Netherlands also publishes a selection of validated key statistics in its data portal, StatLine, leaving no doubt about the reliability of the data and making it retrievable for everyone even after years.[10]

Finally, data enthusiasts can conduct their own analyses using the full datasets from the annual measurements, which include all the responses per library organisation.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the Library Statistics Dashboard, showing the results of the Data Provision Library Act. The graph on the left shows the number of physical loans (by type) of all the libraries in 2023. The graph on the right shows the number of loans per library in the benchmark view. Filters can be used to choose which libraries are shown.

3.2 How are the data used?

Libraries can use the available data and data sources in various ways. As accountability to funders, but also to optimise their own services and increase their impact.

For example, the figures offer increased insight into the target groups the library reaches, how they use the library, and the impact it has on them. This provides an opportunity to tailor services accordingly. In 2024, for example, the Rivierenland Library used data on the number and type of loans to plan its library redesign (Schrijen and Huwaë, 2024d). At the same time, a data source such as the National Library Membership Data Collection also gives insight into who exactly the library is *not* yet reaching, and thus the opportunity to organise very targeted – at municipality and neighbourhood level – campaigns and activities to welcome these target groups to the library nevertheless.

If a library makes changes to its services, the figures can also be used retrospectively to evaluate their impact. For example, Rotterdam Library recently took a step by becoming the first Dutch library to offer a free and fine-free membership for everyone (Goosen, 2025). The results from the Data Provision Library Act can be used in the coming years to monitor what effect this has on the number of members, visitors and loans, as well as on (and in relation to) the library's income and expenditure.

Other libraries will also presumably look at this with interest, and compare the figures with their own. The dashboards in particular lend themselves to benchmarking. The comparison with other libraries makes it clear in which areas your own library is doing well or where there are still gains to be made, and from which other libraries it might be interesting to seek inspiration. An example comes from De Nieuwe Bibliotheek in Almere, where at some point there was a discussion about the use of volunteers. A dive into the data then showed that fewer volunteers were active in the library than in comparable city libraries. In response, the library decided to significantly increase the number of volunteers (Van de Burgt and Klaren, 2024).

Besides libraries, policymakers are an important target group. Long-term statistical series reveal trends and developments that may call for new policies or policy changes. The figures then help shape and later evaluate these policies. For instance, data were used for a financial investment that enabled libraries to further develop cooperation with childcare and education. A similar example is an investment whereby libraries could apply for funding to open new branches or improve existing branches in 2023 and 2024. The Data Provision Library Act supplied input for this by providing greater insight into the housing costs (per m²) of a library branch. In the coming years, the Data Provision Library Act will help to evaluate this investment scheme by showing how the number and type of library locations are changing.

Perhaps most importantly, moreover, data help make the importance of the library understandable, thus providing 'the fuel of

advocacy', so to speak (Gommers, 2025). At national level, this has contributed in recent years to a broad reappraisal of the library, and thus to the government's considerable investment in the library network. And while the library is flourishing, advocacy also remains important at local level, since many municipalities are expected to face financial difficulties and necessary cuts by 2026.

4. Towards a data-mature library network

With the many surveys via (among others) the Library Monitor and the information available on Bnetwerk, there is a strong data foundation under the Dutch library network. There is also a shared ambition in the network to strengthen this foundation in the coming years, by working (even more) data-informed and impact-oriented. Various initiatives and perspectives are working towards this ambition.

For example, the POIs and the KB have been working together in the 'Get More From Data' initiative since 2021. Within this collaboration, a series of national and regional workshops has been organised to help libraries putting data into practice. Participants learn what data and tools are available, and how to introduce and embed these in their work and organisation. The aim is to build a learning network of participating libraries, who know how to find and help each other.

Another network is the Impact Community. Inspiration sessions on impact-oriented working are regularly organised from this network, as well as practical workshops, peer review and coaching sessions and training. The community has also developed an e-learning that allows library staff to gain basic knowledge about impact. The community is also active on the online knowledge-sharing platform Biebtobieb, where inspiration is exchanged and community members help each other with questions.

Finally, a major initiative is the Data Mature Library Network project, which is part of a multi-year trajectory through which the government aims to improve its public services. This project focuses on

technological innovation to increase the data maturity of the library network. It is working on four pillars that are necessary for a future-proof and data-informed library network. These are: common definitions and an underlying set of working principles, easy data collection, raising awareness about the added value of data, and gaining greater insight into the impact on the societal tasks.

The aim is therefore a library network that is increasingly data mature. A network in which every library can use the same resources, knowledge and support around data and research – regardless of how big or small the library is and where it is located.

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6. Endnotes

¹ With sincere thanks to Mirjam Klaren, Anne-Katelijne Rotteveel, Frank Huysmans and Rosemarie van der Veen - Oei for commenting on earlier drafts of this paper.

² An illustration of this is the letter to Parliament 'A subscription to the whole world' of 4 November 2022, in which then State Secretary for Culture and Media Gunay Uslu emphasized the importance of the library, partly on the basis of data, and announced various measures to strengthen the library network.

³ Most library organisations operate in multiple municipalities. The total number of locations includes different types of outlets, such as branches,

(mini) service points, collection points, self-service libraries and stops served by a library bus.

⁴ The islands of Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba are special municipalities within the Netherlands, where the Public Library Facilities System Act also applies. This does not apply to the islands of Curaçao, Aruba and the Dutch part of Sint Maarten, which are self-governing countries within the Kingdom.

⁵ Anyone under 18 in the Netherlands can join the library free of charge, as also stipulated by law. The price of a standard adult subscription varies by library, but is between €40 and €60 per year at many libraries.

⁶ See also <https://www.kb.nl/en/news/dutch-public-libraries-launch-national-ad-campaign> for more information about this campaign.

⁷ All the (Dutch-language) questionnaires can be found as PDFs at <https://www.bibliotheeknetwerk.nl/onderzoek/bibliotheekmonitor>, in the drop-down windows entitled 'Bekijk vragenlijsten van lopende en aankomende jaarlijkse metingen ' and 'Bekijk alle continue vragenlijsten''.

⁸ All reports can be found at <https://kvbboekwerk.nl/consumentenonderzoek/smb-gfk-kwartaalmetingen/archief-consumentenonderzoek>.

⁹ Bnetwerk is a website with information aimed at the library network, including news, policy information, research findings, events and programmes. The research section of Bnetwerk is called Library Insight ('Bibliotheekinzicht'), and can be accessed at <https://www.bibliotheeknetwerk.nl/onderzoek>.

¹⁰ These statistics are available in English at <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/en/dataset/70763eng/table?dl=B275>.